

Volume 15, Issue 2- 2021

Key words: Educational program, caregivers coping, quality of life, chemotherapy.

Introduction:

Cancer is a generic term for a large group of diseases that can affect any part of the body. One defining feature of cancer is the rapid creation of abnormal cells that grow beyond their usual boundaries, and which can then invade adjoining parts of the body and spread to other organs, the latter process is referred to as metastasizing ⁽¹³⁾. Cancer chemotherapy refers to the administration of cytotoxic agents to provide cure, control, or palliation of a neoplasm. Cancer cells are destroyed to the point that cancer can no longer be found in the body, the cancer cells will not grow back. Chemotherapy may keep cancer from spreading or slows its growth. It may also destroy cancer cells that have spread to other parts of body. It may be given as part of palliative care it can be used to shrink tumors that are causing pain or pressure ⁽¹⁴⁾.

Caregivers are the most important physical and emotional care providers. In addition, they need to perform various other activities such as helping the patient cope with symptoms and coordination of medical care. As well as physical care, they also take on emotional care such as enabling social support, helping them make decisions and searching for obtaining information ⁽⁸⁾.

Estimated number of incident cancer cases 2013–2050, during the period 2013–2050, population of Egypt is expected to increase to approximately 160% the 2013 population size. Applying the current age-specific incidence rates to successive populations would lead to a progressive increase in number of incident cases from 114,985 in 2013 to 331,169 in 2050, approximately 290% of 2013 incidence. This increase reflected both population growth and demographic change mainly due to

ageing of population. Population growth alone would increase the number of incident cases by 55.2% in 2015. This fraction progressively decreased to become 32.8% in 2050. The fraction due to ageing gradually increased to reach 67.2% in 2050 ⁽⁹⁾.

Patients with cancer undergoing chemotherapy face serious challenges to their Quality of life (QoL). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), (QoL) defined as individual perception of life, values, objectives, standards, and interests in the framework of culture. The amount of symptoms distressed experienced by an individual has been related to QoL in a number of people with cancer ⁽²⁾.

So the aim of this study has been conducted to improve quality of life of patients undergoing chemotherapy and increase coping levels of chemotherapeutic patients' caregivers.

Aim of the Study:

The study aimed to evaluate the effect of an educational program for the caregivers coping levels and quality of life of their patients undergoing chemotherapy.

The aim was fulfilled through:

- 1- Assess quality of life of patients who are undergoing chemotherapy.
- 2- Assess coping level of chemotherapeutic patients' caregivers
- 3-Develop an educational program for patients and their caregivers regarding (diet, skin care, medication and follow up).
- 4-Implement the educational program .
- 5- Evaluate the effect of the provided program on the caregivers coping level and quality of life for their patients.

Research Hypothesis:

At the end of the study

H I- Coping levels of chemotherapeutic patients' caregivers will be increase after implement the study than before as measured by (**Adaptive coping strategies questionnaire**).

H II- Quality of life of patients who are undergoing chemotherapy will be better after implementing the program than before as measured by (**quality of life assessment questionnaire**).

Methods:

The study was portrayed under the four main designs as follows:

- 1.Technical design.
- 2.Operational design.

3. Administrative design.

4. Statistical design.

1) The technical design:

-It includes research design, setting, subject and tools for data collection.

A) Research design:

A Quasi-experimental research design was used in this study.

B) Setting:

This study was carried out at clinical oncology department in Beni-Suef University Hospital.

C) Subjects:

A Purposive sample of 100 adult patients and 100 caregivers who met the inclusion criteria and agree to participate in the study.

Inclusion criteria for caregivers':-

Both genders, able to read and write and able to communicate clearly.

Inclusion criteria for patient:

Adult male and female patients' diagnosis with cancer, The patients receiving recently chemotherapy and free from any other disease.

D) Tools for data Collection:

Data were collected using the following tools:

First tool (I) Interview questionnaire sheet: It was developed by the researcher, (7,10 & 23): And including two parts e.g:

First tool (A):- it will be concerned with socio demographic data related to patients and caregivers' such as age, gender, level of education, occupation.

First tool (B):- It was used to assess caregiver's level of knowledge regarding chemotherapy.

Scoring system:

Each correct answer was given one degree and the incorrect answer was given zero.

The total score of knowledge it was considered that

- $\geq 75\%$ Satisfactory level of knowledge
- $< 75\%$ unsatisfactory level of knowledge

Tool (II): Adaptive coping strategies questionnaire:

It was adopted from ⁽¹⁹⁾ and it was used to assess adaptive coping styles in caregivers.

Scoring system:

- **low coping:** score from 0 to 25
- **Moderate coping :** score from 26 to 64
- **High coping:** score from 65 to 100

Tool (III) Quality of life scale Index:

It was adopted from ⁽⁴⁾ and it was used to assess the impact of chemotherapy on quality of life of cancer patients.

Scoring system:

the total score ranged from(0) to (114)the grads were given as follow –poor when the total score was less than 60%- fair when the total score 60% to less than 75%- good when total score was 75%to 100%.

Field Work:

- 1- An official permission for conducting the study was obtained from the director of Beni-Suef university hospital and head of oncology department.
- 2- Development of tool I, II &III after reviewing recent relevant literatures.
- 3- Data collection started and completed within 6 months from august (2019) to until the end of January(2020).
- 4- Data collection was done about 7 sessions and it was implemented for 2 days\ week and each session take about 60-90 minutes by the researcher, at the morning shifts.
- 5- Before starting the interview a written consent was obtained from each patient and caregiver after the explanation of the study purpose, patient were interviewed using tools 1,2.
- 6- Also, the caregiver were interviewed using tools 3,4 as pre-test, the interviewing schedule were filled by the researcher for each patient but tools especially of the care giver's filled by the caregiver's each interview last 20-30 minutes depending to patient's capacity to response.
- 7- The researcher were classified the patients into ten groups: each group consisted of 10 patients. Each group attended 7 session. Schedules as 2 session per week for duration of about 8 weeks.
- 8- The program has general objectives and every session has its specific contents and objectives, this was achieved through several teaching methods as, brain storming, lecture discussions and emotional expression role playing and intervention booklet using the following media as computer, video, and pictures.
- 9- At end of each session summery and conclusion was done, let a time for asking question, feedback and give homework assignment for the next session.
- 10- To ensure that the caregivers understand the program content, each session was begun by a summery about what was given through previous session and

at the end of each session the caregivers were oriented about content of the next session by using simple language to suit all patients and caregivers.

4.Statistical Design:

The collected data were organized, categorized, tabulated, and statistically analyzed of the present study was conducted, using the mean, Standard Deviation, Linear Correlation Coefficient and chi-square tests by (*IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 20.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.*). A significant level value was considered when p- value <0.05*, and highly significant level value was considered when p- value<0.001** , while p- value >0.05 indicate non- significant result.

Results:

Table (1): Distribution of the studied patients according to their socio demographic characteristics (n=100).

Items	N	%
Gender		
Male	30	30.0
Female	70	70.0
Age (years)		
20- <35	10	10.0
Mean age 35 or more	90	90.0
Social status		
Single	5	5.0
Married	95	95.0
Residence		
Rural	82	82.0
Urban	18	18.0
Educational level		
Illiterate	58	58.0
Read and write	21	21.0
intermediate	15	15.0
University	6	6.0
Working after disease		
Work	19	19.0
does not work	77	77.0
Student	4	4.0
Nature of work		

Requires a mental effort	3	15.8
Requires a muscular effort	10	52.6
Both	6	31.6
Monthly income for treatment expenses		
Sufficient	32	32.0
Insufficient	68	68.0

Table (2): Distribution of sociodemographic characteristics for care giver's (n=100).

Items	N	%
Age (years)		
<20	4	4.0
20- <35	50	50.0
35 or more	46	46.0
Relationship of kinship to the patient		
husband / wife	20	20.0
parents	5	5.0
Brother	24	24.0
Sons	51	51.0
Gender		
Male	43	43.0
Female	57	57.0
Educational level		
Read and write	36	36.0
intermediate	45	45.0
University	19	19.0
Social status		
Single	19	19.0
Married	78	78.0
Widowed	1	1.0
Divorced	2	2.0
Working		
Work	61	61.0
does not work	39	39.0
Residence		
Rural	80	80.0
Urban	20	20.0

Do you have children		
No	25	25.0
Yes	75	75.0
Do you suffer from health problems		
No	79	79.0
Yes	21	21.0
Type of health problem		
heart	1	4.8
blood pressure	14	66.7
sugar	5	23.8
liver	1	4.8
How many times spend with the patient		
6 hours	14	14.0
12 hours	6	6.0
12 hours	19	19.0
24 hours	61	61.0

Figure (1): Percentage distribution of total knowledge of caregivers regarding chemotherapy (n=100).

Figure (2): Compare between total adaptation level of caregivers regarding to patients undergoing chemotherapy before and after implementation the program (n=100).

p-value was <0.001**.

Table (3): Percentage distribution of studied sample regarding total level of quality of life among patients (n=100).

Total Quality of life scale	Good		Fair		Poor		Chi-square	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	X ²	P-value
Before	24	24	35	35	41	41	25695	<0.001**
After	58	58	25	25	17	17		

p-value was <0.001**

Table (4): Correlation between quality of life before and after with knowledge and coping (n= 100).

Items	Quality of life			
	Before		After	
	r	p-value	r	p-value
Knowledge	0.401	<0.001**	0.230	0.004*
Coping	0.169	0.035*	0.298	<0.001**

p-value was <0.001**

Table (5): Correlation between knowledge before and after and coping (n= 100).

Items	Knowledge			
	Before		After	
	r	p-value	r	p-value
Coping	0.375	0.002*	0.372	<0.001**

p-value was <0.001**

Discussion:

The current study is a Quasi-experimental study aimed to evaluate the effect of an educational program on the caregiver coping levels and quality of life of their patients undergoing chemotherapy.

Regarding the studied patients sociodemographic characteristics, the results of the study revealed that, most of them aged from 35 or more years with a mean age. This might explain that middle adult hood characterized by work and being productive person for both the family and society so feeling not being able to perform social roles could affect coping and quality of life. This result comes in agreement with a study done by ^(16&1). Who found that the majority of sample was in the middle adulthood. While disagreement with⁽³⁾who revealed that the majority of studied patients were 50 years old or more.

Finding of this study showed that, the most of the studies patients were females. This could be due to early of menarche and late age at menopause, null parity, and late age at first pregnancy have been associated with an increased risk of breast cancer. This result comes in agreement with a study done by ⁽²²⁾ who done a research study was titled as " Global cancer in women "who found that the majority of patients were females. These findings were in disagreement with to those of the study done by ⁽¹²⁾ who found that, cancer is more prevalent among males than females.

Regarding the studied caregivers sociodemographic characteristics, the results of the present study revealed that, half of them aged from twenty to less than thirty five years old. This result is disagreement with ⁽⁶⁾ who done a research study was titled as" Caring ability of family caregivers of patients on cancer treatment" who reported that regarding family caregivers with this population, identified that the majority with a mean age of 48.68 years.

Concerning to gender of studied caregivers the present study show that, more than half of caregivers was female and more than three quarters of studied caregivers married This result agreed with ⁽¹⁵⁾ who studied" The burden among family caregivers of elderly cancer patients" who stated that the majority were females and most of the participants were married and have familial responsibilities.

The present study result revealed that, the most of the studied caregivers level of knowledge was highly of knowledge about chemotherapy post program. This could be explained that educate to caregivers knowledge about cancer patients and chemotherapy and give educational program. This study is supported by the research study done by ⁽⁵⁾ who done a research study was titled by "Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Non-Curative Care of Terminally ILL Cancer Patients among Care Takers" who found that the majority of good level of knowledge of caregivers scores post program.

Regarding to caregivers total adaptation level the result of the current study showed that, more than one third reduction level of adaptation among the studied caregivers at before study phases. These findings is in agreement with ⁽¹¹⁾ who found that family caregivers' quality of life is negatively affected during the caregiving process.

Regarding the caregivers total level of adaptation the present study result revealed that, more than two third increase level of adaptation among the studied caregivers at after study phases .This result is in

agreement with ⁽²¹⁾ who found that positive adaptation, and support as factors influencing their QOL. and described expression of feelings and self-esteem, attendance to physical needs, security, and confidence under the Basic Needs Scale, as well as household maintenance, family support as important aspects to improve the strength of caregivers.

Concerning differences between total quality of life pre and post program the current study shows that there is highly improvement in all total dimension of quality of life physical, psychological, social and spiritual state among the studied subject post program than preprogram with highly statistical significance difference. This results explained that educating the patient and family is very important to administration of chemotherapy agent and it is the nurses' responsibilities to educate patients and families. However, ⁽²⁰⁾ found in their study the majority of the interventions led to a positive impact on patient-reported QOL.

While another research by ⁽¹⁸⁾, about Comparison of Quality of life of Cancer Patients Undergoing Chemotherapy reported that the quality of life scoring system did not show significant improvement in all areas of our study, but a provident diagnosis with a suitable treatment including chemotherapy may attenuate the negative aspects of cancer as a lethal disease and as an early indicator of disease progression could help the physician in daily practice to closely monitor the patients.

Finding of this study showed that, there was highly statistically significant correlation deference between quality of life before and after with knowledge and adaptation when p-value was $<0.001^{**}$. And the study carried out by ⁽¹⁷⁾ reported an presence of relationship between the quality of life and the meaning of life in cancer patients and a positive correlation ($p < .001$) was found between the dimensions of the Life meaningfulness scale LMS and factors - religiosity, social support, older age, female gender. A higher sense of life our sample was observable in the population of women with cancer, in patients with a higher level of social support and in religious patients. A positive correlation was recorded in terms of the meaning of life impact on the quality of life.

The current study reveals that there is highly statistically significant correlation deference between total knowledge before and after program with educational level, social status, do you have children and suffer from health problems. This result is supported with ⁽¹¹⁾

who found that there were statistically significant differences in terms of caregivers' gender, education status, employment status, financial status, relationship with patient, and whether caregivers resided with their patients.

Conclusion:

the researcher can conducted that educational program had a positive effect improving quality of life for patients and adaptive coping strategies for caregivers. The study revealed that majority of studied caregivers had satisfactory total level of knowledge, more than two third improvement in the total level of coping among caregivers post program than preprogram. Moreover, more than half highly improvement in the total level of quality of life among the studied patients post program than preprogram. Also, there was highly statistically significant correlation deference between quality of life before and after with knowledge and coping of caregivers.

Recommendations:

In nursing practice:

- Develop a screening and assessment tool to assess quality of life of all patients undergoing chemotherapy.
- Integration of relaxation technique program for patients undergoing chemotherapy.

In nursing program:

- Establish of educational program to educate chemotherapy patients and their families about cancer treatment and to answer their questions.

In further research:

- Replication of the study using a large probability samples acquired from different geographic areas.
- Conduct longitudinal study to assess patients response, adaptation to chemotherapy and coping caregivers process.

List of abbreviations:

Quality of life (QoL).

World Health Organization (WHO).

References:

- (1) **Abd –elmonem G (2014)** the effect of religious activities on recovery of patients with head & neck cancer, thesis for Doctoral Degree in Nursing science. psychiatric and mental health nursing, faculty of nursing Alexandria university. p66.
- (2) **Acton QA (2012)** Issues in Discovery Experimental, and Laboratory Medicine. *Scholarly Editions*.
- (3) **Adamowicz K& Zaucha R (2016)** Evaluation of the impact of cancer treatment on the adoption and consolidation of pro- Health attitudes in the field of cancer in treated patients with colon cancer. *Journal of cancer* 30(I):121-134.
- (4) **Ali SM, Osman ZA, El Malky MI&Zaki MM (2017)**The effect of psycho-educational nursing program on coping and quality of life of patients undergoing chemotherapy. Thesis Doctorate, University of Benha .
- (5) **Babu RL, Mali N, Shinde M (2014)** Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Non-Curative Care of Terminally ILL Cancer Patients among Care Takers. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 2319-7064.
- (6) **Coppetti LD, Girardon- Perlini NM, Andolhe R, de Gutiérrez MG, Dapper SN & Siqueira FD (2018)** Caring ability of family caregivers of patients on cancer treatment: associated factors. *Article Journal*. 10.1590/1518.
- (7) **Garcia MA, Kalecinski J, Oriol M, Bonne A, Lofti M, Espenel S, Tinquaut F, Fournel P, et al., (2018)** Cancer patients treated with intravenous chemotherapy for the first time. *ORIGINAL RESEARCH* Volume 2018:12 Pages 1853—1861.
- (8) **Girgis A, Johnson C, Aoun S, Currow D (2010)** Challenges experienced by informal caregivers in cancer, *CancerForum*;30:21–4.
- (9) **Ibrahim AS, Khaled HM, Mikhail N, Baraka H & Kamel H (2014)** Cancer Incidence in Egypt: Results of the National Population-Based Cancer Registry Program. *Article Journal of Cancer Epidemiology*. 10.1155.
- (10) **Iversen HH& Bjertnaes O (2012)** The Cancer Patient Experiences Questionnaire (CPEQ): Reliability and construct

- validity following a national survey to assess hospital cancer care from the patient perspective. *BMJ*. DOI: 10.1136.
- (11) **Kilic ST& Fatma OZ (2019)** Family Caregivers Involvement in Caring with Cancer and their Quality of Life. *Asian Pac Journal Cancer*, 10.31557.
- (12) **Labib NA, Elraghi H, Shoman T, Fouad HA (2012)** Epidemiology of Oral and Pharyngeal Cancer at the National Cancer Institute. Cairo: *Journal of Cairo University* 80, 85-91.
- (13) **Leon P, Bignold (2019)** Principles of Tumors: A Translational Approach to foundations. 2nd ed. Academic Press.
- (14) **Lister S, Dougherty L& McNamara L (2018)** The Royal Marsden Manual of Cancer Nursing Procedures. *John Wiley & Sons*.
- (15) **Lkhoyaali S, El Haj MA, El Omrani F, Layachi M, Ismaili N, Mrabti H & et al., (2015)** The burden among family caregivers of elderly cancer patients: prospective study in a Moroccan population. *Journal BMC Res*, 10.1186.
- (16) **Lofty A (2012)** the effect of educational program on quality of life of patients undergoing radiotherapy. thesis for Doctoral Degree in Nursing science, Medical and surgical Nursing Faculty of Nursing Benha university, p133.
- (17) **Majerníková L& Obročníková A (2017)** Relationship between the quality of life and the meaning of life in cancer patient. *Journal Pielęgniarstwo*, 10.1515.
- (18) **Mohsin S, Rahman M, Azam N& Mashhadi SF (2016)** Comparison of Quality of life of Cancer Patients Undergoing Chemotherapy in a Tertiary Care Hospital Rawalpindi, *Pak Armed Forces Med Journal*; 66(1):83-87.
- (19) **Pérez MR, Sánchez AA,Ocaña MJ& Casado RD (2017)** Coping strategies and quality of life in caregivers of dependent elderly relatives: *Article Health Qual Life Outcomes*, 15- 71.

- (20) **Senchak JJ, Fang CY & Bauman JR (2019)** Interventions to improve quality of life (QOL) and/or mood in patients with head and neck cancer (HNC): a review of the evidence, *Journal Cancers Head Neck*, 10.1186.
- (21) **Tamayo GJ, Broxson A, Munsell M & Cohen MZ (2010)** Caring for the Caregiver. *Journal Club Article Oncology Nursing Forum*. 37, 1.
- (22) **Torre LA, Islami F, Siegel R, Ward EM & Jemal A (2017)** Global Cancer in Women: Burden and Trends, 10.1158.
- (23) **Yusuf AJ, Adamu A, Nuhu FT (2011)** Caregiver burden among poor caregivers of patients with cancer in an urban African setting. *psycho- oncology*. doi.org/10.1002/pon.1814.